

Kinetics of Silver(I)-catalysed Oxidation of n-Butyl Mandelate by Peroxydisulphate

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Oxidation of organic and inorganic compounds by peroxydisulphate has been reviewed¹. These reactions are very slow at room temperature in absence of catalyst. Silver(I) is the most thoroughly investigated catalyst for these oxidation². Kinetics of oxidation of n-butyl mandelate have not yet been investigated. The present work summarises the results of the oxidation of n-butyl mandelate by peroxydisulphate catalysed by Ag^I.

Results and Discussion

The plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{substrate}]$ is linear indicating the formation of the complex between substrate and the reactive species, and this shows a Michaelis and Menten type of rate-dependence on the substrate. Since the uncatalysed reaction between peroxydisulphate and n-butyl mandelate is extremely slow, there is no significant reaction between ester and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ or between ester and SO_4^- free radical. However, in order to explain the increased rate of disappearance of peroxydisulphate in silver catalysed reaction, postulation of the reactive silver species, probably Ag^{2+} is necessary. Since the reaction product is benzaldehyde and not a keto ester³, it appears that mechanism for the oxidation of n-butyl mandelate is different from the secondary alcohols.

The reaction rate is independent of the [ester] in most of the Ag^I-catalysed oxidations by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. However, in the present study, the rate has been found to depend on the [ester]. This is quite noteworthy. The results can be explained on the assumption that Ag^I in a reaction mixture forms a complex (C⁺) with the substrate and that this

complex reacts with peroxydisulphate in the rate-determining step to form (C₁)²⁺ involving oxidation of Ag^I to Ag^{II} which disproportionates to give PhC[•]H(OH) free radical and Ag⁺ as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2, which is in conformity with the results obtained, has been suggested for the peroxydisulphate oxidation of n-butyl mandelate in presence of Ag^I.

Scheme 2

Application of the steady state approximation and neglecting the variation of $[Ag^{2+}]$, $[PhC^*H(OH)]$ and $[SO_4^-]$ with time, one gets equation (8),

$$\text{Rate} = \left[k_1 + \sqrt{\frac{k_1 k_2 k_4}{k_5}} \right] \frac{[Ester] [Ag^+] [S_2O_8^{2-}]}{(1/k) + [Ester]} \quad (7)$$

$$= k[S_2O_8^{2-}]$$

$$\text{where } k = \frac{A [Ester]}{(1/k) + [Ester]} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and } A = \left[k_1 + \sqrt{\frac{k_1 k_2 k_4}{k_5}} \right] [Ag^+] \quad (9)$$

Thus a plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[ester]$ should be linear as has been observed.

Following conclusion can be drawn from the results of the present investigation. (i) The reaction is first order with respect to [peroxydisulphate]. There is no significant change even by changing the initial [peroxydisulphate]. The values of k were obtained from equation (10) employing the method of least-squares,

$$\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k[S_2O_8^{2-}] \quad (10)$$

(ii) An increase in [ester] increased the rate constant (Table 1). (iii) The rate of reaction is proportional to $[Ag^+]$ (Table 2). (iv) The rate constant increased with increasing acetic acid percentage in the medium. A plot of $\log k$ vs $1/D$ is linear at low $[CH_3COOH]$ having a positive slope. (v) The values of activation parameters are : $\Delta E^\ddagger = 13.75 \pm 0.41 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -12.44 \text{ e.u.}$

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF n-BUTYL MANDELATE

[Substrate] <i>M</i>	$k \times 10^4$ s^{-1}
0.02	0.41
0.025	0.43
0.05	0.59
0.10	0.64
0.30	0.72

Experimental

n-Butyl mandelate was prepared by the literature method⁴. Silver nitrate (B.D.H.) and potassium peroxydisulphate (E. Merck) used were of A.R. grade. All other chemicals used were chemically pure. Potassium peroxydisulphate solution was freshly prepared and its concentration checked by iodometry.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING Ag^+ CONCENTRATION

$[Ester] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Temp.=35°,
Solvent : acetic acid-water = 7 : 3 (v/v)

$[Ag^+] \times 10^3$ <i>M</i>	$k_1 \times 10^4$ s^{-1}	$k_1/[Ag^+]$
1.0	0.34	0.34
2.0	0.69	0.34
3.0	0.92	0.31
4.0	1.10	0.28
5.0	1.62	0.32

The rate of reaction in acetic acid-water (1:1, v/v) was followed by taking out aliquots of the reaction mixture at different intervals of time and determining the concentration of peroxydisulphate left unreacted by reported method⁵. Duplicate rate measurements were reproducible to $\pm 5\%$. The reactions were carried out at 35° keeping $[Ag^+] = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and $[NaOAc] = 0.2 \text{ M}$ (Table 1).

The reaction of peroxydisulphate proceeded at the same rate in the dark and diffused sunlight. Hence rates were measured in the diffused sunlight. since Ag^+ -catalysed oxidation of various substrate follows the same rate laws both in presence and absence of oxygen⁶, no attempt was made to exclude oxygen from the system.

References

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NOTE

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